

CHADA for Electron Channeling Contrast Imaging (ECCI)

Project number	101091621
Project acronym	AddMorePower
Project title	Advanced modelling and characterization for power semiconductor materials and technologies
Start date of the project	1 st January, 2023
Duration	48 months
Call	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01

Responsible organisation	KAI
Editor	Olivia Pfeiler
Dissemination level	PU
Revision	V1.0

Abstract	Structured documentation of CHAracterization DAta (CHADA) gained by carrying out Electron Channeling Contrast Imaging experiments within the AddMorePower project. The structure is based on the final draft of the CWA 17815 created within the framework of the CEN/CENELEC Workshop "Materials characterisation — Terminology and structured documentation". The draft was submitted on Dec. 16, 2024 to CEN/CENELEC.
Keywords	CHADA, Electron Channeling Contrast Imaging, ECCI

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement no. 101091621. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Editor

Olivia Pfeiler (KAI)

Contributors (ordered according to beneficiary numbers)

Claire Chisholm, KAI- Kompetenzzentrum Automobil und Industrieelektronik

Based on

Final Draft CWA 17815 from CEN/CENELEC WS Materials characterization — Terminology and structured documentation, submitted to CEN/CENELEC on Dec. 16, 2024.

Disclaimer

The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The content of this document reflects only the author’s view – the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The users use the information at their sole risk and liability.

Executive Summary

The AddMorePower consortium is dedicated to developing characterization and modelling methods that can meet the unique needs of upcoming power semiconductor technology generations. To achieve effective and efficient research and innovation, a seamless interoperation between materials characterization, materials modelling, and data science is required. This goal can only be accomplished using FAIR and open data practices.

AddMorePower employs the CHADA and MODA methodologies to achieve FAIR data management. These systematic description and documentation methods are used for materials characterization data and materials modelling data, respectively. They are based on a common terminology, concepts and relationships defined by the community, providing a holistic approach to combine data from various materials characterization and modelling techniques, which allows analysing and modelling of complex structures.

In this document a CHADA for Electron Channelling Contrast Imaging (ECCI) experiments is presented, based on the final draft of the CWA 17815 created within the framework of the CEN/CENELEC Workshop “Materials characterisation — Terminology and structured documentation”. The draft was submitted on Dec. 16, 2024, to CEN/CENELEC.

Table of Content

Chapter 1	Introduction	1
Chapter 2	What is ECCI?	2
Chapter 3	Terms and definitions from CHADA v2	3
3.1	batch	3
3.2	calibration data	3
3.3	calibration process	3
3.4	Materials CHAracterisation DAta documentation (CHADA)	3
3.5	characterisation data filtering	4
3.6	characterisation data post-processing	4
3.7	characterisation data processing through calibration	4
3.8	characterisation experiment	4
3.9	characterisation instrument	4
3.10	characterisation laboratory	4
3.11	characterisation measurement process	4
3.12	characterisation outcome	5
3.13	characterisation primary data	5
3.14	characterisation raw data	5
3.15	characterisation secondary data	5
3.16	characterisation signal	5
3.17	characterisation workflow	5
3.18	data pre-processing	5
3.19	data processing	5
3.20	detector	6
3.21	environment	6
3.22	hazard	6
3.23	interaction volume	6
3.24	level of automation	6
3.25	level of expertise	7
3.26	materials system	7
3.27	measurement parameters adjustment	7
3.28	measurement uncertainty calculation	7
3.29	operator	7
3.30	probe	7
3.31	raw data normalisation	8
3.32	reference sample	8
3.33	sample	8

3.34	sample extraction	9
3.35	sample holder	9
3.36	sample inspection	9
3.37	sample preparation	9
3.38	sample preparation parameter	9
3.39	test case	9
3.40	user story	9
Chapter 4	Terms and definitions from ECCI	11
4.1	Threading dislocations (TD)	11
Chapter 5	CHADA v2 for ECCI	12
5.1	CHADA Section 1: User story	12
5.1.1	General	12
5.1.2	Material /materials system	12
5.1.3	Environment and operating conditions	13
5.2	CHADA Section 2: Rationale	13
5.3	CHADA Section 3: characterisation workflow overview	13
5.4	CHADA Section 4: characterisation experiment/ test case documentation	15
5.4.1	General	15
5.4.2	Material/materials system	15
5.4.3	Sample	15
5.4.4	Sample extraction	16
5.4.5	Sample preparation	17
5.4.6	Sample inspection	18
5.4.7	Calibration	20
5.4.8	Measurement parameters adjustment	21
5.4.9	Measurement Process	22
5.4.10	Data processing	23
5.5	CHADA section 5: results analysis	25
Chapter 6	List of Abbreviations	26
Chapter 7	Bibliography	27

Chapter 1 Introduction

The manufacturing industry is facing new challenges with the advent of Industry 5.0. Innovative solutions are required to meet these challenges. The AddMorePower consortium focuses its research on developing necessary characterization and modelling techniques to meet the needs of upcoming power semiconductor technology generations. One backbone to foster research and innovation in this field is the integration of materials characterization, materials modelling, and data science. To enable the fluent interoperability, FAIR and open data practices are needed.

FAIR data management requires harmonized data treatment and harmonized data documentation, not only within the facilities where the simulations and experiments are performed, but across communities. The [EMCC](#) and the [EMMC](#) developed two methodologies for a systematic description and documentation of materials CHARACTERIZATION DATA (CHADA) and materials MODelling Data (MODA). In AddMorePower we make use of the developed concepts and terminology from CHADA and MODA to describe the produced data in a harmonized way and to share the gained knowledge in the community.

CHADA is a systematic description and documentation method for material characterization experiments, including user case, raw data generation and post-processing of the data. It enables the systematic investigation of materials. A harmonized experiment documentation is essential for managing material science data and for guiding the development of e.g. new materials that meet specific requirements. CHADA provides the basis for a holistic approach to combine data from different characterization techniques, which enables the analysis and modelling of complex structures and links between different experiments. It is based on a common terminology, concepts and relationships defined by the community [1]. In 2024 the common terminology and structured documentation was revised by a consortium within the CEN/CENELEC workshop "Materials characterisation — Terminology and structured documentation", resulting in the final draft CWA 17815, which was submitted to CEN/CENELEC on Dec. 16, 2024.

The CHADA terminology and structured documentation presented in this document is based on the final draft of the CWA 17815 from Dec. 2024. This CHADA is called "CHADA v2"

Chapter 2 What is Electron Channelling Contrast Imaging (ECCI)?

Electron contrast channelling imaging (ECCI) is an electron diffraction technique performed in a Scanning electron microscopy (SEM). It is used primarily to visualize and characterize defects in materials such as dislocations, stacking faults, grain boundaries, inclusions, etc. An Electron channelling pattern (ECP), which carries the reciprocal space information from the crystal, can be used to orient the sample into a diffraction condition, also sometimes known as a channelling condition. In this geometry, with the incident beam near a Bragg condition, the contrast arising from defects will be visible. There are two main types of diffraction conditions: (1) the electron beam is diffracted from a single set of planes in a 2-beam diffraction condition, or (2) from multiple sets of planes, in a multi-beam condition. By orienting the sample into a 2-beam condition, with the incident electron beam near the Bragg condition, information from a single set of planes is probed and this can be used to determine information from defects, where contrast rules depend on diffraction vector and the crystallographic information of the defect – for example the Burgers vector of a dislocation.

Chapter 3 Terms and definitions from CHADA v2

For the purposes of this document, the following terms and definitions apply.

ISO and IEC maintain terminological databases for use in standardization at the following addresses:

— ISO Online browsing platform: available at <http://www.iso.org/obp/>

— IEC Electropedia: available at <http://www.electropedia.org/>

3.1 Batch

Specific quantity of material produced or processed at one time, under the same conditions.

Note 1 to entry The term batch is often used in manufacturing and production industries to track, control, and ensure the quality of materials. Each batch typically has a unique identifier and may be subject to quality control measures to ensure consistency and compliance with quality standards.

3.2 Calibration data

Output data of a measurement on a reference sample by a specific measuring instrument/device/system.

Note 1 to entry Calibration data are post-processed into corrections to be used to correct measured characterization data or to perform uncertainty calculations.

3.3 Calibration process

Operations/actions under specified conditions that are needed to obtain the correction used to convert the signal of the characterization measurement (as produced by the detector) into the raw characterization data.

EXAMPLE 1 In nanoindentation, the electrical signal coming from capacitive displacement gauge is converted into a calibrated raw-displacement data.

EXAMPLE 2 In nanoindentation, the electrical signal coming from capacitive displacement gauge is converted into a real raw-displacement signal after using a proper calibration function (as obtained by the equipment manufacturer). Then, additional calibration procedures are applied to define the point of initial contact and to correct for instrument compliance, thermal drift, and indenter area function to obtain the real usable displacement data.

Note 1 to entry Within this workflow, a possible way is to use a reference sample (with pre-defined, specific, and stable physical characteristics and known properties) for the interaction with the measurement probe, in order to extract characterization data to be compared to predefined values. In this way, the accuracy of the measurement tool and its components (for example the probe) is evaluated and confirmed.

3.4 Materials CHAracterization DAta documentation (CHADA)

Set of forms that document materials characterization.

3.5 Characterisation data filtering

In data processing, process on a dataset to exclude, rearrange, or apportion data according to certain criteria.

Note 1 to entry Preprocessing of raw data (for example, compacting data, removing outliers, filtering noise, interpolating missing data) is one type of characterization data filtering.

Note 2 to entry The processing can include hardware filters (such as low pass filters "hardwired" to the sensor/probe).

3.6 Characterisation data post-processing

Data analysis and transformation that allows to calculate the material property/behavior from the calibrated primary data.

Note 1 to entry Characterization data post-processing involves the application of a method, based on some theory or model, to primary data to calculate the secondary data that provide information about the characterization property or behavior.

Note 2 to entry Characterization data post-processing includes digital image processing to enhance or extract useful information.

EXAMPLE 1 In nanoindentation testing, the Oliver-Pharr method is used, which allows calculating the elastic modulus and hardness of the sample by using the load and depth measured signals.

EXAMPLE 2 Analysis of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (or optical) images to gain additional information, for example microstructural analysis, grain size evaluation, digital image correlation procedures.

3.7 Characterisation data processing through calibration

Process that describes how signal data are corrected and/or modified based on calibrations into raw data.

3.8 Characterisation experiment

Execution of one specific characterization workflow.

Note 1 to entry The term "test case" is typically used for a characterization experiment carried out to assess quality or performance against a defined reference or standard.

3.9 Characterisation instrument

Device used for executing characterization actions to characterize a material, alone or in conjunction with one or more supplementary devices.

3.10 Characterisation laboratory

Laboratory where a whole process or some of its stages take place.

3.11 Characterisation measurement process

Process of experimentally obtaining data (values) that are attributed to a sample.

3.12 Characterisation outcome

Digestion and/or judgement of the output of one or several tests given as feedback to the owner of the user story.

3.13 Characterisation primary data

Data resulting from applying corrections to normalize and/or harmonize characterization raw data, in order to prepare them for post-processing.

3.14 Characterisation raw data

Output data of the characterization measurement given by the measuring instrument.

3.15 Characterisation secondary data

Data resulting from the application of characterization data post-processing.

Note 1 to entry Characterization secondary data may represent a property or a behavior.

Note 2 to entry Characterization secondary data may be used to establish a materials relation for a simulation model.

3.16 Characterisation signal

Result (effect) of the interaction between the sample and the probe or between the samples, which usually is a measurable and quantifiable quantity.

Note 1 to entry Characterization signal is usually emitted from a characteristic "emission" volume, which can be different from the sample/probe "interaction" volume and can be usually quantified using proper physics equations and/or modelling of the interaction mechanisms.

Note 2 to entry According to IUPAC Compendium of Chemical Terminology, a "signal" is "A representation of a quantity within an analytical instrument".

3.17 Characterisation workflow

process composed of all necessary steps (for example, sample preparation, calibration, measurement, post-processing) to establish the property, behavior or image of a material or materials system.

3.18 Data pre-processing

process of curation (or preparing) data, which may come from disparate data sources, to improve their quality or reduce bias in subsequent analysis.

Note 1 to entry If this process is applied to characterization the input is raw data and the output is primary data.

3.19 Data processing

computation that provides a data output following the elaboration of some input data, using a data processing application possibly exploiting a data processing model.

3.20 Detector

physical device (or chain of devices) that is used to measure, quantify and store the signal generated by interaction of the probe with the sample.

EXAMPLE 1 Back Scattered Electrons (BSE) and Secondary Electrons (SE) detectors for SEM.

EXAMPLE 2 Displacement and force sensors for mechanical testing.

3.21 Environment

Surrounding medium.

EXAMPLE 1 Environment of the material or materials system that appear(s) in the user story.

EXAMPLE 2 Medium that surrounds the characterization sample in the experiment.

3.22 Hazard

set of inherent properties of a substance, mixture of substances, or a process involving substances that, under production, usage, or disposal conditions, make it capable of causing adverse effects to organisms or the environment, depending on the degree of exposure (that is, a source of danger).

3.23 Interaction volume

The volume of material, and the surrounding environment, that interact with the probe or samples and generate a detectable (measurable) signal (information).

Note 1 to entry In some cases, the volume of interaction could be different from the volume of detectable signal emission. For example, in SEM, the volume of interaction between the electron probe and the material is different from the volumes that generate the captured signal.

EXAMPLE 1 In x-ray diffraction, the interaction volume is the volume of material that interacts directly with the x-ray beam and is usually smaller than the volume of the entire sample. Depending on sample's structure and microstructure, the interaction between the sample and the x-ray incident beam generates a secondary (reflected) beam that is measured by a detector and contains information on certain sample's properties (for example, crystallographic structure, phase composition, grain size, residual stress).

EXAMPLE 2 In SEM, the interaction volume is the volume of material that directly interacts with the incident electron beam, it is usually much smaller than the entire specimen's volume and can be computed by using proper models. The interaction between the scanning probe and the sample generates a series of detectable signals (for example back scattered electrons, secondary electrons, x-rays, specimen current) which contain information on, for example, sample morphology, microstructure, and composition.

3.24 Level of automation

Degree to which tasks are executed by machines using a specified protocol.

3.25 Level of expertise

Specific experience, education, training and/or certifications required to carry out a task.

Note 1 to entry This field is typically relevant only for materials testing in regulated environments.

Note 1 to entry The level of expertise in the CHADA may just be specified as low/medium/high or in a more de- tailed way with respect, for example, to operator qualifications or certifications for certain test techniques.

3.26 materials system

Two or more materials that are in contact and/or interacting.

EXAMPLE Tribological properties (such as friction and wear) are not properties of a material, but properties of a system of two or more interacting bodies (for example, samples or components interacting with test probes or interfacial surfaces, non-destructive testing of machine components, inspection of materials in manufacturing processes). Consequently, multiple materials might be involved (for example, a polymeric and a metallic sample moving in a lubricated contact, or a sample subjected to chemical treatment).

3.27 Measurement parameters adjustment

Set of operations carried out on a characterization measurement system using a sample which is not a reference sample so that it provides values considered to be correct for a quantity being measured.

Note 1 to entry Adjustment of a measuring system is different to calibration, which is sometimes a prerequisite for adjustment. Adjusting/tuning a measuring instrument is an activity without a reference sample (which would be a calibration). The output of this process can be a specific measurement parameter to be used in the characterization measurement process.

Note 2 to entry After an adjustment of a measuring system, the measuring system is usually recalibrated.

3.28 Measurement uncertainty calculation

In data processing, the determination of the statistical dispersion of the values attributed to a measured quantity.

3.29 Operator

The human person who takes care of the entire process or any of its sub-processes/stages, including operating the test equipment.

3.30 Probe

A physical device or radiation (matter or field, together called a physical) that interacts with the sample and generates a response called signal.

Note 1 to entry	The probe is used to acquire information on the specimen's behavior and properties.
Note 2 to entry	In tribological characterization and other techniques that investigate systems, a probe may be hard to define.
EXAMPLE 1	In x-ray diffraction, the probe is a beam of x-rays with known energy that is properly focused on the sample's surface with a well-defined geometry.
EXAMPLE 2	In electron microscopy (SEM or TEM), the probe is a beam of electrons with known energy that is focused (and scanned) on the sample's surface with a well-defined beam-size and scanning algorithm.
EXAMPLE 3	In mechanical testing, the probe is a force actuator that is designed to apply a force over-time on a sample. Many variants can be defined depending on way the force is applied (for example, tensile/compressive uniaxial tests, bending test, indentation test) and its variation with time (for example, static tests, dynamic/cyclic tests, impact tests).
EXAMPLE 4	In dynamic light scattering, temporal fluctuations of backscattered light due to Brownian motion and flow of nanoparticles are the probe, resolved as function of pathlength in the sample. From fluctuation analysis (intensity correlations) and the wavelength of light in the medium, the (distribution of) diffusion coefficient(s) can be measured during flow. The Stokes-Einstein relation yields the particle size characteristics.
EXAMPLE 5	In spectroscopic methods, the probe is a beam of light with pre-defined energy (for example in the case of laser beam for Raman measurements) or pre-defined polarization (for example in the case of light beam for Spectroscopic Ellipsometry methods), that is properly focused on the sample's surface with a well-defined geometry (specific angle of incidence).

Commented [CC(M1)]: it is only a focused and scanned probe in SEM or STEM. In TEM the beam is not focused or scanned.

3.31 Raw data normalisation

Data processing which involves adjusting raw data to a notionally common scale.

Note 1 to entry	It involves the creation of shifted and/or scaled versions of the values to allow post-processing in a way that eliminates the effects of influences on subsequent properties extraction.
Note 2 to entry	Raw data normalization is one type of preprocessing of raw data.

3.32 Reference sample

Sample that is sufficiently homogeneous and stable with reference to one or more specified property(ies), which has been established to be fit for its intended referencing use in measurement or in examination.

3.33 Sample

Portion of the material or materials system selected for characterization or testing.

Note 1 to entry	The term 'sample' implies the existence of a sampling error, that is, the results obtained on the portions taken are only estimates of the property/behavior present in the parent material.
-----------------	--

- Note 2 to entry Typically, the term is further qualified, for example, bulk sample, representative sample, primary sample, bulked sample, test sample.
- Note 3 to entry An alternate term is specimen. Sample and specimen are sometimes used interchangeably, or also with slightly different meanings.
- Note 4 to entry In fields such as composites, the term coupon is used to denote a sample.

3.34 Sample extraction

Act of extracting a portion (amount) of material from a larger quantity of material. This operation results in obtaining a sample representative of the batch with respect to the property or properties being investigated.

- Note 1 to entry The term can be used to cover either a unit of supply or a portion for analysis. The portion taken may consist of one or more sub-samples and the batch may be the population from which the sample is taken.
- Note 2 to entry This operation is meant to obtain a sample representative of the material with respect to the property or properties being investigated.
- Note 3 to entry The portion taken may consist of one or more sub-samples and the (sub-) samples may be the population sample representing the material.
- Note 4 to entry This can be applied to a batch of materials produced (population from which the sample is taken).

3.35 Sample holder

An object which supports the specimen in the correct position for the sample preparation.

EXAMPLE An example of sample holder is microtome holder.

3.36 Sample inspection

Analysis of the sample to determine information that is relevant for the subsequently applied characterization method.

EXAMPLE In the nanoindentation method, sample inspection is carried out by means of scanning electron microscopy to determine the indentation area.

3.37 Sample preparation

Sample preparation processes (for example, machining, polishing, cutting to size) are executed before actual observation and measurement.

3.38 Sample preparation parameter

Settings of devices used for sample preparation.

3.39 Test case

Characterization experiment carried out to assess quality or performance against a defined reference or standard.

3.40 User story

A high-level description of the problem, including the material, the environment in which it functions and the properties/behavior to be determined or explained.

Note 1 to entry There are no details related to the characterization process, which is to be decided on by the characterization expert.

Chapter 4 Terms and definitions from ECCI

For the purposes of this document, the following terms and definitions apply.

4.1 <a>-type, <c>-type, <a+c>-type dislocations

<a>, <c>, and <a+c> refer to the dislocation Burgers vectors $b=1/3\langle 11-20 \rangle$, $b=\langle 0001 \rangle$, and $b=1/3\langle 11-23 \rangle$, respectively. These are the expected dislocation Burgers vector types for dislocations at the GaN surfaces analysed.

4.2 B/C adjustments

Brightness and contrast (B/C) adjustments made to acquired images

4.3 Stub

A small, non-magnetic platform to which the sample is affixed, which is then attached to the microscope stage.

4.4 Threading dislocations (TD)

Dislocations which span the device layers and have a line direction nominally parallel to the wafer growth direction, $\langle 0001 \rangle$.

4.5 Wafer notch and anti-notch

Processed wafers have multiple levels of alignment features. The most obvious, is the wafer notch. This is the 6 o'clock position of the wafer. The anti-notch is the 12 o'clock position. The crystallographic direction of the wafers produced for AddMorePower are $\langle 11-20 \rangle$, from the notch to the anti-notch.

...

Chapter 5 CHADA v2 for ECCI

In this chapter the CHADA for ECCI experiments performed in the project AddMorePower is presented. The CHADA is based on the common terminology defined in the CEN Workshop Agreement 17815 [1] and the revised templates provided by the CEN/CENLEC Workshop from 2024.

CHADA authors:

Claire Chisholm, KAI- Kompetenzzentrum Automobil und Industrieelektronik

Version:

V1.0

Release date:

17.11.2024

5.1 CHADA Section 1: User story

5.1.1 General

Table 1 —User story

User story	
Name	ECCI Acquisition
Description	Generate a multi-image ECCI two 2-beam dataset
Client/requester	Jakob König

5.1.2 Material /materials system

Table 2 —Material/materials system

Material	
Name	C:GaN
Description	A carbon doped GaN LUT structure
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>
Further documentation	Wafer with stack:

<p>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</p>	
---	---

5.1.3 Environment and operating conditions

Table 3 — Environment and operating conditions

Operational context	
Description	ThermoFisher Scientific Apreo 2S SEM operated in immersion mode at 15kV, 1.6nA, 5mm WD. A scan rotation is applied so that <11-20> is always horizontal.
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>

5.2 CHADA Section 2: Rationale

Table 4 —Rationale

Rationale	
Description	ECCI is used to research dislocations in materials
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>

5.3 CHADA Section 3: characterisation workflow overview

Table 5 — Characterization workflow metadata

Characterization Workflow metadata	
Name	C:GaN threading dislocation characterization
Description	Two 2-beam ECCI TD analysis workflow, beta version
Sample(s) to be tested	5 digit sample ID
Test method(s) and environment(s)	<i>(see Table 6</i>
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>
Laboratory	KAI MSS
Operator	KAI MSS ECCI expert

Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>
-----------------------	---

Table 6 — Characterization workflow diagram

Diagram	
<p>The diagram illustrates the characterization workflow. It begins with 'Sample extraction (Cleaving)', followed by 'Sample preparation (Sample Mounting)', and 'Measurement process (SEM session)'. A 'Microscope alignment' step is shown above the measurement process. The workflow then enters a 'Data processing' phase, which includes 'Image pre-processing (B/C adj., cropping)', 'Reference measurement (Diffraction vector angle measurement)', and 'Image analysis (B-W contrast angle measurement)'. The process concludes with 'Raw data (.SIF images)' and 'Characterization results (excel table)'.</p>	
Link to diagram	<i>(In case there is a publicly available version of the diagram)</i>

5.4 CHADA Section 4: characterisation experiment/ test case documentation

5.4.1 General

Each experiment and/or test procedure should be documented by using the following template tables. If several materials or samples are tested at one time or if a time series is measured, the measurements can be kept together by considering entities to be lists or arrays.

Time series measurements can be document by considering all boxes to be arrays. In this way, all measurements in a set can be documented together in one CHADA.

Table 7 and table 8 document the material/materials system and sample(s) to be investigated in some detail. These have grey headers.

In tables 9 to 16, and in the BPMN diagram, the characterisation workflow is documented, consisting of different processes (shown with blue headers) and datasets (magenta) as inputs and outputs. Here the material(s) and sample(s) are referenced just by data their unique identifier and/or unique name.

5.4.2 Material/materials system

Table 7 —Material/materials system

Material/materials system	
Name	C:GaN
Identifier(s)	
Description	A carbon doped GaN LUT structure
Process history	<i>(including manufacturing steps or other prior processing information that describes the state of the material)</i>
Physical structure	Wafer with stack:
Composition / Chemical structure	GaN Hexagonal
Properties known prior to the characterisation	

5.4.3 Sample

Table 8— Sample

Sample

Name	carbon doped GaN LUT structure
Identifier	5 digit sample ID
Description	The sample is cleaved from the wafer and attached to aluminium stub with silver paint. The <11-20> (direction from wafer notch to anti-notch) is noted on the stub.
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>
Dimensions	~1cm x ~2cm
Physical structure	GaN LUT
Material composition / Chemical structure	See Table 7 —Material/materials system
Other sample properties	
Hazard	<i>(link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>

5.4.4 Sample extraction

Table 9— Sample extraction

Sample Extraction		
Name (unique)	Cleaving	
Description	The sample is cleaved by hand from the wafer	
Input: materials data	Material	C:GaN LUT
	Provider	Infineon Technologies Austria
	Identifier	1
	Description	Wafer piece
Laboratory	KAI MSS	
Operator	KAI MSS ECCI expert	
Instrument	Name	None, manual step
	Manufacturer	None, manual step
	Model	None, manual step

	Unique ID	None, manual step
Level of expertise of the operator and/ or laboratory capabilities	Experienced staff <i>(with reference to relevant standards)</i>	
Level of automation	Manual; not automatable <i>(Describe what can be automated in the process)</i>	
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>	
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>	
Output (Sample)	5 digit sample ID	

5.4.5 Sample preparation

Table 10 — Sample preparation

Sample preparation	
Name (unique)	Sample Mounting
Description	After the sample is cleaved from the wafer, it is attached to aluminium stub with silver paint. The <11-20> (direction from wafer notch to anti-notch) is noted on the stub.
Input: sample data	47562 <i>(unique name or ID of sample, see also sample section for a detailed description of the sample)</i>
Input	<i>(from other steps of this characterisation procedure, other procedures or external data)</i>
Laboratory	KAI MSS
Operator	KAI MSS ECCI expert
Instrument	Name
	Manufacturer
	Model
	Unique ID
Holder	Al pin stub
Parameters	<i>(settings for the preparation)</i>

Commented [CC(M2)]: Same comment as above

Environment	Description	
	Properties	
Level of expertise of the operator and/or laboratory capabilities	Expert electron microscopist <i>(with reference to relevant standards)</i>	
Level of automation	Manual; not automatable	
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>	
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>	
Output: prepared sample data		

5.4.6 Sample inspection

For the ECCI experiments sample inspection is not carried out.

Table 11— Sample inspection

Sample inspection		
Name (unique)		
Description		
Input: sample data	<i>(unique name or ID of sample, see also sample section for a detailed description of the sample)</i>	
Input	<i>(from other steps of this characterisation procedure, other procedures or external data)</i>	
Laboratory		
Operator		
Instrument	Name	
	Manufacturer	
	Model	
	Unique ID	
Parameters	<i>(settings for the preparation)</i>	

Level of expertise of the operator and/or laboratory capabilities	<i>(with reference to relevant standards)</i>
Level of automation	
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>
Output	

5.4.7 Calibration

Table 12 – Calibration

Calibration		
Name (unique)	Microscope calibration	
Description	The SEM is already calibrated	
Input: reference sample data	<i>(specify in case of a reference sample, reference material or a certified reference material)</i>	
Input	<i>(from other steps of this characterisation procedure, other procedures or external data)</i>	
Laboratory		
Operator		
Instrument	Name	ThermoFisher Scientific Apreo 2S
	Manufacturer	ThermoFisher Scientific
	Model	Apreo 2S
	Unique ID	
Parameters	<i>(settings for the preparation)</i>	
Level of expertise of the operator and/or laboratory capabilities	<i>(with reference to relevant standards)</i>	
Level of automation		
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>	
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>	
Output: calibration data		

5.4.8 Measurement parameters adjustment

Table 13 – Measurement parameters adjustment

Measurement parameters adjustment		
Name (unique)	SEM alignment	
Description	Standard microscope alignment procedure is performed at the start of the session, after tilting near to the tilts used for ECCI (~14deg) and a stage bias of 600V was applied.	
Input: sample data	<i>(unique name/id of the sample, see also sample section)</i>	
Input	<i>(from other steps of this characterisation procedure, other procedures or external data)</i>	
Laboratory	KAI MSS	
Operator	KAI MSS ECCI expert	
Instrument	Name	ThermoFisher Scientific Apreo 2S
	Manufacturer	ThermoFisher Scientific
	Model	Apreo 2S
	Unique ID	
Parameters	<i>(settings for the preparation)</i>	
Level of expertise of the operator and/or laboratory capabilities	Experienced electron microscopist <i>(with reference to relevant standards)</i>	
Level of automation	Manual steps; some could be automated	
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>	
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>	
Output: adjusted settings for the instruments		

5.4.9 Measurement Process

Table 14 – Measurement Process

Measurement Process		
Name (unique)	SEM session	
Description	Acquire a set of SEM images at two different diffraction conditions.	
Input: sample data	5 digit sample ID	
Input	<i>(from other steps of this characterisation procedure, other procedures or external data)</i>	
Laboratory	KAI MSS	
Operator	KAI MSS ECCI expert	
Instrument	Name	ThermoFisher Scientific Apreo 2S
	Manufacturer	ThermoFisher Scientific
	Model	Apreo 2S
	Unique ID	
Parameters	<i>(settings for the preparation)</i>	
Probe	Electrons	
Interaction volume		
Detector	T1, T2, T3	
Environment	Description	High vacuum
	Properties	
Characterisation signal		
Level of expertise of the operator and/or laboratory capabilities	Expert electron microscopist <i>(with reference to relevant standards)</i>	
Level of automation	Manual (could be automated)	
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>	
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>	
Output: raw data	Images in .tiff format	

5.4.10 Data processing

Table 15 — Data processing (1)

Data processing (1)	
Name	Image pre-processing
Description	Register the g1 and g2 images, number each dislocation, crop an area (~100pixels) around each dislocation, adjust the B/C to make the TD B-W contrast obvious
Input	SEM images in .tiff format <i>(raw data, primary data)</i>
Type of data processing	Image registration, numbering of TDs, cropping, B/C adjustments
Data processing model	
Data processing software	
Laboratory	KAI MSS
Operator	KAI MSS ECCI expert
Level of expertise of the operator and/or laboratory capabilities	Experienced electron microscopist <i>(with reference to relevant standards)</i>
Level of automation	Manual, but could be automated
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>
Output	Pre-processed SEM images in .tiff format

Table 16 – Data processing (2)

Data processing (2)	
Name	Diffraction vector angle measurements
Description	Diffraction vector angle measurements
Input	Pre-processed SEM images in .tiff format
Type of data processing	Image registration, numbering of TDs, cropping, B/C adjustments
Data processing model	
Data processing software	

Laboratory	KAI MSS
Operator	KAI MSS ECCI expert
Level of expertise of the operator and/or laboratory capabilities	Experienced electron microscopist <i>(with reference to relevant standards)</i>
Level of automation	Manual, but could be automated
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>
Output	List of diffraction vectors angle measurement

Table 17 – Data processing (3)

Data processing (3)	
Name	Image analysis – B-W contrast measurements
Description	Measure B-W contrast direction from white to black. A +/- 5deg allowance from orthogonal to the diffraction vector is considered orthogonal.
Input	Pre-processed SEM images in .tiff format & diffraction vector angle measurement
Type of data processing	Measurement of B-W contrast direction and comparison to g1 and g2
Data processing model	
Data processing software	MS Excel
Laboratory	KAI MSS
Operator	KAI MSS ECCI expert
Level of expertise of the operator and/or laboratory capabilities	Experienced electron microscopist <i>(with reference to relevant standards)</i>
Level of automation	Manual, but could be automated
Reference to standard	<i>(Add reference to standard, if any)</i>
Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>
Output	List of angle measurement

5.5 CHADA section 5: results analysis

Characterisation results		
Characterisation results 1	Input	List of diffraction vectors angle measurement
	Method	If B-W_angle1 is orthogonal to g1 AND if B-W_angle2 is orthogonal to g2, then the TD is c-type. Please note, a +/- 5deg allowance from orthogonal to the diffraction vector is considered orthogonal. <i>(description including method by which results were obtained across several characterisation procedures or test series)</i>
	Output	List of c-type TDs
	Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>
Characterisation results 2	Input	List of diffraction vectors angle measurement
	Method	If B-W_angle1 is EQUAL TO B-W_angle2, then the TD is a-type. Please note, there is a +/- 5deg angle allowance. The a-type B-W contrast is also quite a bit smaller than the a+c and c-type TDs.
	Output	a-type TDs
	Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>
Characterisation results 3	Input	List of diffraction vectors angle measurement
	Method	If the TD is not c-type and it is not a-type then it is a+c type.
	Output	a+c type TDs
	Further documentation	<i>(Link to a relevant document/web resource)</i>

Chapter 6 List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
B/C	Brightness/Contrast
B-W	Black-White
BSE	Back-scattered Electron
CHADA	Materials Characterization Data
ECCI	Electron Channelling Contrast Imaging
ECP	Electron Channelling Pattern
EMCC	European Materials Characterization Council
EMMC	European Materials Modelling council
g1, g2	Diffraction vector #1, diffraction vector #2
GaN	Gallium Nitride
LUT structure	Layer Under Test structure
KAI	Kompetenzzentrum Automobil- und Industrieelektronik
kV	kilovolt
ms	milliseconds
MSS	Materials Science and Simulation
SE	Secondary Electron
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
Si	Silicon
TD	Threading Dislocations
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
WD	Working Distance

Chapter 7 Bibliography

- [1] [CWA 17815 – Materials characterisation – Terminology, metadata and classification](#), January 2025
- [2] [CWA 17284 – Materials modelling – Terminology, classification and metadata](#), October 2018
- [3] Emmc.eu, [MODA template](#), 2021.
- [4] Emmc.eu, [MODA workflow template](#), 2021.
- [5] M. Sebastiani, C. Charitidis, E. P. Koumoulos, [CHADA docx detailed forms](#), Zenodo, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2637419>
- [6] M. Sebastiani, C. Charitidis, E. P. Koumoulos, [Main Introduction to the CHADA concept and case studies](#), Zenodo, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2636609>